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Teaching Vocabulary and Writing skills through short film “Snake Bite”

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Abstract

Aim of this paper is to see effectiveness of teaching vocabulary and writing skills to students through short movie “Snake bite”. The researcher included 30 students in the control group and another 30 students in the Experimental group. The researcher took pre-test of students of controlled group and experimental groups. He taught vocabulary and writing skills by using short film “snake bite”. Post-test was also taken of all students to observe improvement. Post-test of Experimental group shows the development of vocabulary and writing skills compared to the control group

Introduction:

Now teachers are dealing with such students who are born and brought up with mobile and Internet. Teaching with old approach may be futile. New generation want everything immediately. They are easily distracted. They are looking for fun and entertainment in the classrooms. New generation is much interested in movies and web series. It is challenging task of teachers to keep their interest alive in classroom. Teaching English through short movies can be very entertaining way to teach them. Researcher experimented on students by teaching them through traditional methodology and teaching them by short movie “Snake bite”.

Hypothesis of research

- Teaching vocabulary and writing skills can be effective way through short film “Snake bite”

- Active learning Methodology can keep interest of students alive
- Short film “snake bite” can motivate students to learn English
- Teaching English through short films can provide entertain and fun to learn English.

Objective of research

- To see efficiency of teaching English through short films
- To observe building vocabulary and writing skills of students
- To check whether short films provide entertainment or not in teaching English.
- To contribute in the domain of ELT

Research Methodology

Researcher in this study selected 100 students of BBA for Experiment. Students were divided into an experimental group and controlled group. 50 students were

included in the experimental group and another 50 students were included in the control group. Researcher took Pre-test of Both groups control group and experimental group. Researcher taught students of control group through traditional way. students of the experimental group were taught by the researcher through the English short film "Snake bite" In the end, the Result of Pre-test and Post-test is matched. Control group and experimental group are compared. The researcher has not selected a random assignment so he has selected quasi-experimental design.

Experiment

Researcher composed following worksheet to teach vocabulary and writing skills. Speed of video was decreased little bit for better comprehension as it was American accent.

(A) Answer following question

(1) Who gives idea to take dylen to camp?

(2) What does Xavier suggest to save Dylen?

(3) What does Tyler do to save Dylen?

(4) What is idea of Cole to save Dylen?

(B) Match words with meaning

1	Venom	to remove (something) by cutting
2	Scream	poisonous substance secreted by animals such as snakes
3	chop off	give a long, loud, piercing cry or cries

(C) Make sentences of following words.

(1) Venom _____

(2) Scream _____

(3) Chop off _____

Control group shows development around 2% in post-test where Post-test of Experimental group shows development around 12%. Development is observed much in vocabulary and writing skills...

Finding of research

Present study finds that short films 'Snake bite' is effective to teach vocabulary and writing skills of students. Students can improve pronunciation. Speaking also can be improved. Students take active participant when they are taught through short films. Students like to learn from short films.

Conclusion

Students are clever. Teachers have to be cleverer to teach them, Short films can be better source to teach them. Present study motivate future researcher to explore more. Future research can select some other students to make experiment. Present research contributes in the field of ELT. Educators can get benefit of this finding to update their teaching style.

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